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BeefSC: A model for calculating optimal stocking rates and costs of beef

Description of model (v. 1.0) and input data for application on Brazilian beef production

Stefan Wirsenius

Francisco d'Albertas Gomes de Carvalho

DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND ENERGY SCIENCES

CHALMERS UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
Gothenburg, Sweden 2026
www.chalmers.se

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Summary

Background

Brazil produces beef primarily in pasture-based systems, and large differences in pasture productivity and herd performance translate into large differences in beef output per hectare. Increasing productivity per hectare can lower land requirements per unit of beef and can, under appropriate governance, reduce incentives for further pasture expansion into forest frontiers.

Objective

We developed BeefSC (Beef Stocking-rate and Cost model), a spatially explicit model that estimates optimal stocking rates, beef yields, and production costs across Brazil under four stylized beef systems that represent increasing production intensity.

Methods

The framework combines (i) a stocking-rate optimization module implemented in R and (ii) an enterprise cost module implemented in Excel. The stocking-rate module calculates monthly herbage growth, senescence, and grazing availability and then identifies the stocking rate that maximizes liveweight gain per hectare while respecting seasonal feed constraints and herd maintenance requirements. The module represents a full-cycle herd split into adult animals (cows, breeding bulls, and unweaned calves) and growing animals, allocates pasture area between these cohorts, and estimates cohort-specific intake and weight change across wet and dry seasons. For semi-intensive systems, the module adds dry-season concentrate supplementation and, for the most intensive system, a feedlot finishing period for steers.

The cost module translates the optimized biophysical outputs into pixel-level costs by combining detailed operational and fixed cost accounts with spatially varying prices for major inputs. For inputs with geographically varying farm-gate prices (notably fertilizer, lime, and purchased feed), the model adds transport costs from the nearest regional supply center. For outputs, the model estimates transport costs of live animals to slaughterhouses using a raster-based least-cost framework that integrates road infrastructure, freight cost coefficients, and slaughterhouse locations.

Beef systems evaluated

“Extensive 1” represents a low-intensity baseline with no annual nitrogen fertilization of pastures and no purchased feeds beyond mineral salt and urea; pastures renew every 25 years and cattle are pure-breed Nelore.

“Extensive 2” adds annual nitrogen fertilization (capped at $200 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) and regular liming; pastures renew every 15 years.

“Semi-intensive” 1 adds dry-season concentrate feeding for growing steers on top of the Extensive 2 pasture management.

“Semi-intensive 2” adds a three-month feedlot finishing period for steers, with a ration dominated by maize grains and silage and smaller shares of soybean meal, urea, and mineral salt.

Key results

Across pixels, median total costs per hectare rose strongly with intensity (R\$710 ha⁻¹ in Extensive 1; R\$1,730 ha⁻¹ in Extensive 2; R\$2,290 ha⁻¹ in Semi-intensive 1; and R\$3,210 ha⁻¹ in Semi-intensive 2). Higher yields moderated the increase in cost per kilogram of carcass, but did not eliminate it (median R\$16.6 kg⁻¹ in Extensive 1; R\$19.3 kg⁻¹ in Extensive 2; R\$18.8 kg⁻¹ in Semi-intensive 1; and R\$23.2 kg⁻¹ in Semi-intensive 2).

The cost structure shifted from fixed-cost dominance in low-productivity systems toward operational-cost dominance as intensity increased. Fixed costs accounted for 40% of total costs in Extensive 1 but only 16% in Semi-intensive 2, while fertilizer, lime and purchased feed shares increased markedly with intensification. Spatial variation in costs per kilogram was largest in Extensive 1 because fixed costs spread over low outputs in low-productivity pixels.

Median stocking rates increased from 1.3 AU ha⁻¹ in Extensive 1 to 2.2–2.5 AU ha⁻¹ in the more intensive systems. Median herbage intake rose from 3.9 Mg DM ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ to 6.9 Mg DM ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Median carcass production tripled from 46 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in Extensive 1 to 140 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in Semi-intensive 2. Liveweight gain per animal unit also increased with intensity (0.16 to 0.28 kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹), reflecting higher intake per animal and a higher share of pasture allocated to growing animals in fertilized systems.

Transportation costs constituted a small share of total costs in all systems, but the framework captured substantial geographic differences in delivered input costs and market access through explicit transport modeling to regional supply centers and slaughterhouses.

Interpretation

The results illustrate a central trade-off: intensification substantially raises beef output per hectare and reduces the land requirement per unit of beef, but it increases total costs per hectare and can increase unit costs when expensive purchased feeds and feedlot operations dominate. Systems that rely primarily on improved pastures and moderate supplementation can deliver large yield gains with smaller unit-cost penalties than systems that depend heavily on purchased feeds.

Implications

BeefSC provides a transparent, spatially explicit tool for exploring how alternative productivity trajectories in Brazilian beef systems affect cost competitiveness and land-use pressure. Combining the modeled yield gains with deforestation governance and supply-chain enforcement can help translate productivity improvements into real land sparing in the Amazon and adjacent regions.

1. Introduction

Rising global food demand continues to put pressure on tropical forests. Population growth, rising per-capita incomes, and diet shifts toward land-intensive meat and dairy products together raise demand for land.

The Brazilian Amazon and Cerrado sit at the center of this land squeeze. Forest conversion in those areas has been strongly linked to agricultural expansion, and cattle ranching has remained a dominant proximate driver over long periods. Basin-wide analyses of land-use change find that, during key expansion phases, increases in pasture area closely track deforestation dynamics, while cropland growth often follows pasture or replaces already cleared land (Barona et al., 2010).

Improving beef yield per hectare (for example, through fertilizer inputs and feed supplementation) could, in principle, reduce pressure to expand pasture areas. The land-sparing logic is straightforward: if Brazil can produce the same or higher volumes of beef from existing pasture areas, it can meet demand with less additional clearing—provided that policies and market conditions prevent rebound expansion. Life-cycle analyses of Brazilian systems show that higher productivity—achieved through improved pastures, supplements, and in some cases feedlot finishing—can cut the area needed per unit of carcass output and lower emissions intensity, even when additional inputs raise some non-land emissions (Cardoso et al., 2016). Taken together, literature supports the view that higher beef yield per hectare can help mitigate climate change in Brazil by limiting pasture expansion and associated deforestation, but only when paired with strong forest governance and supply-chain enforcement.

To connect beef intensification to land sparing and climate mitigation, analysis needs to quantify a practical core question: what levels of stocking rate and management inputs deliver the highest beef output per hectare, and what do those productivity gains cost—across the highly heterogeneous conditions found in Brazil? Answering that question helps clarify the economic feasibility of intensification pathways that could reduce pressure to expand pasture into forests, and it provides the yield-and-cost components needed to assess whether intensification—paired with effective forest governance—can contribute to avoided deforestation and lower CO₂ emissions.

This report presents BeefSC, a model that calculates optimal stocking rates in grazing-based beef production systems and the associated production costs. Here, “optimal” denotes the stocking rate that yields the highest beef output per hectare per year under biophysical feed constraints, recognizing strong seasonality in pasture growth and limits on animal performance during the dry season. BeefSC is designed to operate with gridded (spatially explicit) data, enabling systematic comparison of low-yield extensive systems and higher-yield systems that rely on improved pasture management, fertilization and liming, and (in some cases) supplemental feeding and feedlot finishing.

The report further documents the input data and demonstrates the model through an application to beef production in Brazil, generating spatially resolved estimates of output, stocking rates, and costs under a set of stylized systems with either currently low or higher yield per hectare. By quantifying both the productivity potential and the cost implications of intensification across space, the Brazilian application helps place beef intensification in a policy-relevant frame: it indicates where intensification can most plausibly raise output per hectare and where it may be costly, thereby informing strategies aimed at increasing production on existing pasturelands while supporting land sparing and climate mitigation through reduced deforestation pressure.

2. Model description

The BeefSC model consists of two soft-linked modules, a “stocking rate” module and a “cost” module. In the stocking rate module, the stocking rate that maximizes beef yield per hectare and per year is calculated for each pixel. The output from the stocking rate module in terms of stocking rate, grazed herbage intake per year, beef production per year, and use of fertilizer, supplementary feed and other inputs per year, is the input to the cost module, which calculates pixel-specific operational and amortized fixed costs for the production.

2.1 Stocking rate module

The stocking rate module returns the stocking rate that results in the maximum beef yield per hectare and year for each pixel (or polygon). For a specified herbage (pasture) productivity per hectare, specified monthly, the module calculates the monthly ad libitum intake of herbage and, from that, the resulting liveweight gain for growing (non-adult) animals. By varying the stocking rate, the module identifies the stocking rate that gives the highest liveweight gain per hectare per year.

Finding this stocking rate is an optimization problem, for several reasons:

- First, the potential herbage intake by an individual animal is indirectly influenced by the herbage intake by all other animals in the grazing paddock, that is, by the stocking rate in the paddock. At a higher stocking rate, more animals contribute to the liveweight gain per hectare, but it also means a higher aggregate herbage intake per hectare, and therefore, a lower potential intake for each individual animal.
- Second, herbage growth is cyclical, with high growth rates during the wet and/or warm season, and zero or close to zero growth during the dry/cold season. For systems that use only little or no supplementary feed (in addition to grazed herbage) during the dry/cold season, the stocking rate must be high enough to profit from the high herbage availability in the wet/warm season, but low enough to avoid large weight losses and mortality during the dry/cold season.
- Third, the level of herbage intake impacts the state of the herbage plant, in terms of growth and tillering. If intake is excessive, growth is significantly reduced.
- Fourth, for full cycle beef systems, the fraction of the paddock used by growing weaned animals should be large enough to enable the highest possible liveweight growth of these animals, but small enough to provide herbage to cows and calves sufficient for their maintenance and milk production (cow) and growth (calf).

The stocking rate module is programmed in R. The script is available on request to S. Wirsenius.

2.1.1 Indices and notation

Indices:

- $i \in I$: pixel
- $t \in T$: month
- $c \in C = \{\text{adult + unweaned calves, male growing, female growing}\}$: animal cohort
- $p \in P = \{\text{adult+calves paddock, growing (male+female) paddock}\}$: grazing paddock

- $f \in F = \{\text{maize grains, soymeal, cotton seed, maize silage, urea, mineral salt}\}$: supplementary feed component
- $n \in N = \{\text{urea fertilizer, NPK fertilizer, lime, seeds}\}$: fertilizer and other inputs
- $q \in Q = \{\text{wet/warm, dry/cold}\}$: season
- $s \in S = \{\text{Extensive 1, Extensive 2, Semi-intensive 1, Semi-intensive 2}\}$: beef system

Main quantities

- $LWG \{i,s\}$: liveweight gain per hectare of grazed land per year
- $LWG^{AU} \{i,c,s\}$: liveweight gain per animal unit (AU) per day
- $SR \{i,p,s\}$: stocking rate in animal unit (AU) per hectare of grazed land
- $HI^{yr} \{i,s\}$: herbage intake (grazed) per hectare per year
- $HI \{i,t,p,s\}$: herbage intake per hectare per month i and paddock p
- $HI^{AU} \{i,c,s\}$: herbage intake per animal unit (AU) per day

2.1.2 Beef herd characteristics

In the stocking rate optimization routine (see section 2.1.6), the beef herd is characterized using these variables:

- $LW_{c,s}$ [kg] – liveweight of animal cohort c in system s
- $LWG_{i,t,c,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — liveweight gain of grazing animals in kg per day per animal unit in pixel i , month t , animal cohort c , and system s (see section 2.1.5).
- $LWG_{feedl,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — liveweight gain of feedlot animals in kg per day per animal unit in system s .
- η_s [1] – carcass yield (carcass quantity in percent of liveweight)
- θ_s [1] – fraction (on AU basis) of herd consisting of weaned growing animals on pasture
- ι_s [1] – fraction (on AU basis) of herd consisting of cows and unweaned calves on pasture
- ε_s [1] – fraction (on AU basis) of herd in feedlot
- γ_s [1] – fraction (on AU basis) of growing animals on pasture consisting of male animals

The herd is divided into two main cohorts: i) *adult+calves*, which includes cows, breeding bulls and unweaned calves, and ii) *growing* animals, which includes weaned calves, also replacement heifers. This distinction is made for making pixel-specific estimates of the area fraction (of total grazed area in the pixel) required for cows (and adult bulls), whose liveweight must be maintained (i.e., net liveweight gain over the year should be approximately zero) to ensure sustained production of calves. The remainder of the grazed area is allocated to growing animals, and, hence, is the pixel-specific area fraction available for liveweight gain production. Hence, in addition to stocking rate, the routine also includes optimization with respect to paddock areas (as a fraction of total grazed area in the pixel) allocated to adult and growing animals, respectively (see section 2.1.6 for further details).

In addition to the division into adult and growing animals, the latter is further subdivided into male and female cohorts. This distinction is made because male cattle have larger mature liveweights than

female cattle, and, therefore, also have higher potential liveweight gain rates at a given pasture herbage availability. In addition, in some systems, male growing animals are offered a different dry-season ration that includes concentrate supplements (see section 2.1.4).

The model also represents cattle feeding in confinement (i.e., feedlots). The main application of feedlot feeding is finishing of stockers from grazing operations. Number of animals in feedlot is expressed as a fraction of the total herd (on animal unit basis, as average over the year), stated exogenously (cf. Table 2).

For simplicity, the values of all herd characteristic variables, except $LWG_{i,t,c,s}^{AU}$, are fixed across all pixels (cf. Table 2). The values represent steady-state averages over the entire production cycle, which, for full-cycle beef systems, can be considered the cow's lifetime (roughly 10 years). The simplification of constant herd structure means that the optimal stocking rate value in any one pixel is constant over the optimization period (one year). The thereby introduced error contributes to a slight underestimation of the true optimal stocking rate, since herd managers, particularly in extensive systems, strive to adjust calving and slaughter times so that herd size (and its total feed energy requirements) is lowest during periods of low herbage availability.

All variables are on an animal unit (AU) basis, not actual heads. Animal unit equivalents are defined as the normalized metabolic liveweight ($\text{weight}^{0.75}$) against a liveweight of 450 kg.

2.1.3 Herbage growth and intake

In the stocking rate optimization routine, herbage growth and intake are represented monthly. As mentioned above, in extensive systems, in which the feed resource is almost exclusively grazed herbage, the optimal stocking rate is largely a trade-off problem between weight gains in the wet season and avoidance of weight losses in the dry season. Monthly time steps are used for herbage availability to offer a more precise basis for assessing this trade-off problem.

Herbage intake by grazing animals is, under most conditions, constrained by herbage availability, mainly in terms of herbage mass density per unit area and sward height. Among the many existing experiment-based estimates of this constraint, the Beef SC model uses the function originally developed by Johnson and Parsons (1985):

$$HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU} = \max HI_{c,t}^{AU} \frac{\left(\frac{LAI_{i,t,p,s}}{K}\right)^q}{1 + \left(\frac{LAI_{i,t,p,s}}{K}\right)^q} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where:

$HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU}$ [kg DM AU⁻¹day⁻¹] — herbage intake in kg dry matter per day per animal unit (AU) for pixel i , month t , animal cohort c , and system s

$\max HI_{c,t}^{AU}$ [kg DM AU⁻¹day⁻¹] — maximum herbage intake in kg dry matter per day per animal unit (AU) for animal cohort c in month t belonging to either wet/warm or dry/cold season

$LAI_{i,t,p,s}$ [1] — leaf area index in pixel i , month t , paddock p , and system s

q and K are constants

The maximum daily herbage intake reflects constraints on feed intake due to physical and metabolic factors, particularly body size and rumen passage rate. The latter is strongly influenced by feed digestibility (McDonald et al., 2011). Maximum daily herbage intake is approximated with RUMINANT estimates of *ad lib* intake (see section 2.1.5). The values of the q and K constants depend on animal size and species. The constant K equals $0.229 \times LW^{0.36}$ (Herrero et al., 2000), and q is 3 in all cases.

The leaf area index, $LAI_{i,t,p}$ (dimensionless), is calculated according to:

$$LAI_{i,t,p,s} = 10^{-5} SLA_{i,t,p,s} \lambda_{i,t,p,s} HP_{i,t,p,s}^{avg} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where:

$SLA_{i,t,p,s}$ [cm^2 (g DM leaf mass) $^{-1}$] — specific leaf area per unit of dry matter of leaf mass in pixel i , month t , paddock p , and system s

$\lambda_{i,t,p,s}$ [1] — the fraction of leaf mass (of total plant mass above ground) in pixel i , month t , paddock p , and system s

$HP_{i,t,p,s}^{avg}$ [kg DM ha^{-1}] — the average herbage mass pool above ground in pixel i , month t , paddock p , and system s

The average herbage pool $HP_{i,t,p}^{avg}$ in month t is calculated as the pool by the *end* of month $t-1$, plus pool changes during month t caused by growth, senescence and intake. To calculate the average herbage pool over a month, we assumed a linear time trend for all monthly changes. Equations for average and end values of the herbage pool can hence be written as:

$$HP_{i,t,p,s}^{avg} = HP_{i,t-1,p,s}^{end} + \frac{1}{2} \times (HG_{i,t,p,s} - HS_{i,t,p,s} - HI_{i,t,p,s}) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$HP_{i,t,p,s}^{end} = HP_{i,t-1,p,s}^{end} + HG_{i,t,p,s} - HS_{i,t,p,s} - HI_{i,t,p,s} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where:

$HP_{i,t,p,s}^{end}$ [kg DM ha^{-1}] — the herbage pool above ground at the end of month t

$HG_{i,t,p,s}$ [kg DM ha^{-1}] — the growth of herbage during month t

$HS_{i,t,p,s}$ [kg DM ha^{-1}] — the senescence (to surface) of herbage during month t

The variable $HI_{i,t,p,s}$ ($\text{kg dry matter ha}^{-1}$) is herbage intake and equals:

$$HI_{i,t,p,s} = 30.4 HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU} SR_{i,p,s} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where:

$HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU}$ [$\text{kg DM AU}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$] — herbage intake in kg dry matter per day per animal unit in pixel i , month t , animal cohort c , and system s (see Eq. 1)

$SR_{i,p,s}$ [AU ha^{-1}] — stocking rate in animal unit (AU) per hectare of grazed land in pixel i , paddock p , and system s

2.1.4 Fertilizer and lime inputs, supplementary feed and feedlot feeding, and labor use

The stocking rate optimization routine includes an endogenous calculation of the annual use of nitrogen fertilizer and lime inputs, which serves as the basis for pixel-specific cost calculations. The BeefSC model calculates both nitrogen fertilizer and lime inputs as a function of the herbage intake, since the intake correlates closely to the quantities required to maintain soil nitrogen and pH status. The values of these coefficients are fixed across all pixels (cf. Table 9).

The model also calculates the use of fertilizer, lime and seeds when renewing permanent pasture areas. This is calculated as a quantity per hectare of pasture land (cf. Table 10). The quantities are annualized over the stated lifetime of the pasture.

Grazing-based beef production systems are the main application of the stocking rate optimization in the Beef SC model. But grazing-based systems often include the use of supplements, such as mineral salt, and in slightly more intensive systems, also the use of concentrate feeds, particularly in the dry/cold season. The use of supplementary feed is stated exogenously, in kg intake per animal unit per day, specified separately for the wet/warm and dry/cold seasons (cf. Table 9). The values of these coefficients are fixed across all pixels.

Feed use in feedlots is calculated in the same way as for supplements, in kg intake per animal unit per day (cf. Table 9). Animal units here refer to animals in the feedlot only, not the entire herd.

The model also represents the use of labor for various purposes. Some of the labor use is included in cost coefficients in the cost module (see sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3). However, labor for livestock management is calculated using an hourly coefficient per number of animals per year (cf. Table 9).

2.1.5 Liveweight gain

For grazing animals, pixel-specific liveweight gains (and losses) are calculated as a function of feed intake. These functions are emulations based on the RUMINANT model (Herrero et al., 2013), which estimates potential (*ad lib*, i.e., to appetite) feed intake, digestion, and performance of individual ruminant animals. Here, these emulations refer to RUMINANT predictions of liveweight changes for a prescribed feed intake, below *ad lib* intake, since actual feed intake is assumed to be limited by herbage availability (see section 2.1.3). The emulated functions are written as second-order polynomials:

$$LWG_{i,t,c,s}^{AU} = \phi (HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU})^2 + \chi HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU} + \psi \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where:

$LWG_{i,t,c,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — liveweight gain in kg per day per animal unit in pixel i , month t , animal cohort c , and system s

$HI_{i,t,c,s}^{AU}$ [kg DM AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — herbage intake in kg dry matter per day per animal unit in pixel i , month t , animal cohort c , and system s (see Eq. 1)

ϕ , χ and ψ are coefficients derived by regression analysis of prescribed herbage intake and resulting herbage intake returned from the RUMINANT model (cf. Table 8).

For feedlot animals, liveweight gains are stated exogenously (cf. Table 2).

2.1.6 Stocking rate optimization

As mentioned above, the “optimal” value of the cattle stocking rate in each pixel is the value that gives the highest cattle liveweight production of growing animals (i.e. non-adult) per unit area over the course of the optimization period (one year). The optimization problem can be written as:

$$\text{maximize: } LWG_{i,grow,s} = \sum_{t=1}^{12} 30.4 \alpha_{i,s} SR_{i,grow,s} [\gamma_s LWG_{i,t,male,s}^{AU} + (1 - \gamma_s) LWG_{i,t,female,s}^{AU}] \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$\text{subject to: } LWG_{i,dry,adult,s}^{AU} > \text{min}LWG_{i,dry,adult,s}^{AU} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

by varying: $SR_{i,grow,s}$, $\alpha_{i,s}$

where:

$LWG_{i,grow,s}$ [kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹] — liveweight gain of growing animals in kg per hectare per year in pixel i and system s

$\alpha_{i,s}$ [1] — is the paddock size, as a fraction of the total grazed area, allocated to growing animals in pixel i and system s

$SR_{i,grow,s}$ [AU ha⁻¹] — stocking rate in the paddock for growing animals in pixel i and system s

$LWG_{i,t,male,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — liveweight gain in kg per day for growing males in pixel i , month t , and system s

$LWG_{i,t,female,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — liveweight gain in kg per day for growing females in pixel i , month t , and system s

γ_s [1] — fraction (on AU basis) of growing animals on pasture consisting of males in system s (see section 2.1.2)

$LWG_{i,dry,adult,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — liveweight gain in kg per day for adult animals during the dry/cold season in pixel i and system s

$\text{min}LWG_{i,dry,adult,s}^{AU}$ [kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹] — the minimum liveweight gain in kg per day for adult animals during the dry/cold season in pixel i and system s

As the mathematical formulation shows, the routine identifies not only the optimal stocking rate, but also the optimal allocation of grazing area to growing animals vs adult animals, expressed by the variable $\alpha_{i,s}$, which is the grazing paddock size allocated to growing animals (as a fraction of total grazed area). The purpose is to identify the largest possible fraction of grazing area allocated to growing animals, to maximize their liveweight gain. However, the maximum paddock size of growing animals is constrained by the need for a sufficiently large paddock for adult animals, i.e. cows, to ensure that their liveweight and reproductive capacity is maintained. The fertility of cows tends to fall if they experience prolonged periods of large weight loss. This constraint is formulated as a maximum weight loss during the dry/cold season (Eq. 8).

Once the optimal stocking rate and paddock sizes have been found, the routine outputs pixel-specific values of variables that are used as inputs in the cost module:

- Average stocking rate on grazed land for growing and adult animals
- Total herbage intake per hectare of agricultural land per year
- Use of fertilizer, lime, seeds, and labor per hectare of agricultural land per year
- Use of supplementary and feedlot feeds per hectare of agricultural land per year
- Total liveweight production per hectare of agricultural land per year
- Total beef carcass production per hectare of agricultural land per year, specified separately for male growing, female growing, feedlot animals, and adult animals

The average stocking rate of all animals, $SR_{i,s}$ [AU ha⁻¹], in pixel i and system s is calculated according to:

$$SR_{i,s} = SR_{i,grow,s} \frac{\alpha_{i,s}}{\theta_s} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where:

$\alpha_{i,s}$ [1] — is the paddock size, as a fraction of the total grazed area, allocated to growing animals in pixel i and system s

θ_s [1] — fraction (on AU basis) of herd consisting of weaned growing animals in system s

The total herbage intake per hectare of agricultural land per year, $HI_{i,s}^{yr}$ [kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹], in pixel i and system s is calculated according to:

$$HI_{i,s}^{yr} = \sum_{t=1}^{12} [HI_{i,t,grow,s} + HI_{i,t,adult,s}] \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where:

$HI_{i,t,p,s}$ [kg ha⁻¹ month⁻¹] — monthly herbage intake in the paddocks of growing and adult animals, respectively, in pixel i and system s (see Eq. 5)

The recurring (annual) use of fertilizer and lime is calculated as total herbage intake per hectare per year (Eq. 10) multiplied by a coefficient (cf. Table 9). The use of fertilizer and lime for pasture renewal is calculated as a coefficient multiplied by pasture area. The use of labor is calculated as a coefficient (hours per animal unit per year) multiplied by the average stocking rate.

The use of supplementary feed is calculated as the feed coefficient in kg per animal unit per day (cf. Table 9) multiplied by the stocking rate and the length of the wet/warm and dry/cold seasons, respectively. Use of feedlot feed is calculated as the feed coefficient in kg per animal unit per day multiplied by the stocking rate and the share of animals in the feedlot per all animals in the herd.

Total annual liveweight per hectare of animals to slaughter is the sum of the liveweight gain of growing animals, $LWG_{i,grow,s}$, and adult animals, $LWG_{i,adult,s}$. Beef carcass production per hectare per year is calculated as the liveweight production multiplied by the carcass yield (cf. Table 2), specified for each animal category.

2.2 Cost module

This module implements a pixel-level enterprise cost model for beef production. The basis of the module is a detailed account of the variable and fixed costs of grazing-based beef. For cost items with constant prices across pixels (most items except fertilizer and supplementary feed), the module calculates a set of cost coefficients based on this detailed account. The module then applies these cost-coefficients to the pixel-specific estimates of stocking rates and herbage intakes from the stocking-rate module (see section 2.1.6) to produce pixel-specific estimates of the on-farm production costs.

For cost items whose prices vary by pixel (primarily due to transportation costs), the module calculates the cost for each item separately at the pixel level. In addition, for fertilizer and lime applied annually and supplementary feed, quantities are pixel-specific, calculated in the stocking rate module (see section 2.1.6).

The pixel-specific annual on-farm costs are divided by the pixel-specific annual output in the form of live animals sold for slaughter (see section 2.1.6) to obtain the farm-gate cost per kg of output. Transportation costs to abattoirs are added to this to obtain the cost per kg at market.

The cost module is programmed in Excel. Files are available on request to S. Wirsenius.

2.2.1 Indices and notation

Indices:

- $i \in I$: pixel
- $u(i)$: state containing pixel i
- $r \in R$: regional center
- $k \in K^{var}$: operational (variable) cost items
- $j \in K^{fix}$: fixed cost items (assets/infrastructure)
- $f \in F$: supplementary feed components
- $s \in S = \{\text{Extensive 1, Extensive 2, Semi-intensive 1, Semi-intensive 2}\}$: beef systems

Main quantities

- $q \{i,s,k\}$: quantity driver for operational cost item k (e.g., kg/ha/yr fertilizer)
- $p \{i,s,k\}$: farm-gate price for item k (including transportation costs from regional center)
- $C^{var} \{i,s,k\}$ denotes the annual operational (variable) cost for item k
- $I \{i,s,j\}$: initial investment cost for fixed item j
- $Dep \{i,s,j\}$: annual depreciation of fixed item j

2.2.2 Operational costs

The BeefSC model includes the following operational cost items:

- **Fertilizer and lime.** Purchase costs of urea, ammonium nitrate, PK fertilizer, NPK fertilizer, and lime; costs for application of fertilizer and lime (labor, fuel, etc.).
- **Purchased feed and supplements.** Purchase costs of maize grains, soybean meal, cottonseed, maize silage, urea (as feed), and mineral salt.
- **Animal-related costs.** Purchased animals (breeding bulls), vaccines, and veterinary and medical services.
- **Machinery and equipment use.** Operating costs (labor, fuel, etc.) for machinery and equipment (other than for fertilizer and lime application).
- **Maintenance.** Repair of fences, waterers, and machinery, equipment and other facilities (labor, materials, etc.)
- **Labor.** Labor for pasture and livestock management (other than labor listed above).
- **Financial and administration.** Interest on operating capital, property tax, and administration.

Operational costs $C_{i,s}^{var}$ [R\$ year⁻¹] for pixel i and beef system s are computed as the sum of annual quantity $q_{i,k,s}$ [kg year⁻¹] for cost item k , multiplied by the corresponding farm-gate price $p_{i,k}$ [[R\$ kg⁻¹]:

$$C_{i,s}^{var} = \sum q_{i,k,s} p_{i,k} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

For some cost items, the model calculates pixel-specific farm-gate prices. In the case of purchased fertilizer, feed and supplements, farm-gate prices are calculated as the price $p_{r,k}$ at the nearest regional center r plus the transportation cost from the regional center to the pixel:

$$p_{i,k,s} = p_{r,k,s} + \tau_k d_{i,m(k)} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

where:

τ_k [R\$ km⁻¹] — transportation cost per km for commodity k

$d_{i,r}$ [km] — distance from pixel i to the nearest regional center r

2.2.3 Fixed costs

The BeefSC model includes the following fixed cost items:

- **Pasture establishment.** Includes cost for seeds, fertilizer, lime, machinery, and labor.
- **Cows.** Purchasing cost of breeding cows.
- **Fences:** Perimeter and internal fences.
- **Watering facilities:** Waterers, pipes.
- **Buildings and handling infrastructure.** Includes corral and chute, feed bunks, machinery depot, feedlot, feed storage and processing depot.
- **Machinery and equipment.**

Fixed costs are annualized using depreciation over the lifetime and add-ons for interest and insurance costs:

$$Dep_{i,s,j} = \frac{I_{i,j,s} - SV_{i,j,s}}{L_{j,s}} + \iota \cdot \frac{I_{i,j,s} - SV_{i,j,s}}{2} + \kappa I_{i,j,s} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

where:

$Dep_{i,s,j}$ [R\$ year⁻¹] — annualized cost of fixed item j

$I_{i,s,j}$ [R\$] — initial cost of fixed item j

$SV_{i,s,j}$ [R\$] — salvage value cost of fixed item j

$L_{s,j}$ [year] — lifetime of fixed item j

ι [1] — interest rate (annual cost of investment capital)

κ [1] — insurance cost as a fraction of the initial cost

2.2.4 Pixel-specific operational and fixed costs

To reduce the computing power needed for calculations of costs at the pixel level, the cost items with constant prices are detailed in sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3 are aggregated and scaled to three key variables: i) pasture area, ii) stocking rate, and iii) annual herbage intake per hectare of pasture, see Table 1 for a complete list. These cost coefficients are then applied to the pixel-specific estimates of stocking rates ($SR_{i,s}$, Eq. 9) and herbage intakes ($HI_{i,s}^{yr}$, Eq. 10) from the stocking-rate module (see section 2.1.6) to produce pixel-specific estimates of the on-farm production costs.

Table 1 Cost coefficients for cost items with constant prices across pixels. The table shows annual cost coefficients, their scaling unit and specific cost items included in each coefficient. Costs for fertilizer, lime, purchased feed, supplements, and labor are calculated using pixel-specific prices, see text.

Coefficient	Scaling unit	Cost items included in coefficient
Operational costs		
Pasture labor and machinery	per ha pasture	Labor and machinery cost in pasture operation (other than application of inputs)
Pasture fertilizer and lime application	per Mg herbage intake	Labor and machinery cost for application of inputs
Breeding bulls	per animal unit (AU)	Purchase cost of breeding bulls
Vaccination, vet & medical	per animal unit (AU)	Costs for vaccines, vet attendance,
Machinery other than for pasture	per animal unit (AU)	Fuel, labor etc for machinery; non-feedlot and feedlot
Repairs	per ha pasture	Repair of fences, waterers, and other facilities
Interest on operating capital	per operational cost excl. interest and taxes	Interest cost on operating capital (operating capital = half of operational cost)
Property taxes	per ha pasture	Property taxes
Administration, etc.	per operational cost excl. interest and taxes	Administration costs, etc.
Fixed costs		
Pasture establishment excl. fertilizer and lime	per ha pasture	Amortized costs of seeds, machinery, and labor for establishing pasture
Animals	per animal unit (AU)	Amortized costs of stock of cows
Fences	per ha pasture	Amortized costs of perimeter and internal fences
Waterers	per ha pasture	Amortized costs of waterers
Buildings	per animal unit (AU)	Amortized costs of buildings
Machinery	per animal unit (AU)	Amortized costs of machinery other than for pasture establishment

For cost items whose prices vary by pixel (primarily due to transportation costs), the module calculates the cost for each item separately at the pixel level. In addition, for fertilizer and lime applied annually and supplementary feed, quantities are pixel-specific, calculated in the stocking rate module (see section 2.1.6).

The pixel-specific annual on-farm costs are divided by the pixel-specific annual output in the form of live animals sold for slaughter to obtain the farm-gate cost per kg of output (see section 2.1.6). The costs for transportation to abattoirs are added to this to obtain the cost per kg at market (see section 2.2.5).

2.2.5 Pixel-specific transportation costs

The BeefSC model includes costs for transportation of fertilizer, feed and supplements from nearest regional center to the farm, i.e., pixel (cf. Eq. 12). For lime and silage, it includes the transportation costs from the nearest producer. The model also includes costs for the transportation of animals to the nearest abattoir.

3. Input data and results for Brazilian beef production

3.1.1 Spatial structure

All spatial analyses were conducted on a regular grid covering Brazil, defined in the WGS 84 geographic coordinate system. The grid has a spatial resolution of approximately 0.09° (~10 km at the Equator), with cell size varying slightly in east–west distance with latitude. All input datasets were harmonized to this projection and resolution to ensure spatially consistent cell-level calculations of stocking rates, beef yields, and production costs.

3.1.2 Beef systems

We defined four beef systems with different levels of productivity:

- **Extensive 1:** A low-intensity system with no annual application of nitrogen fertilizer on pasture areas, and no use of supplementary feed except mineral salt and urea. The pasture areas are seeded with *Brachiaria decumbens* and are renewed every 25 years. Cattle are pure-breed Nelore.
- **Extensive 2:** As Extensive 1, but nitrogen fertilizer is applied on pasture areas, with a maximum rate of 200 kg N per ha per year. Lime is also applied regularly. The pasture areas are renewed every 15 years.
- **Semi-intensive 1:** As Extensive 2, but concentrates are offered to growing steers during the dry season.
- **Semi-intensive 2:** As Semi-intensive 1, but steers are finished in feedlots during a three-month period.

Extensive 1 is the most prevalent type of beef production system in Brazil today. The other systems are intended to assess the potential increases in beef yield per hectare when yield-increasing measures are applied incrementally. This design resembles those of similar analyses. (Cardoso et al., 2016; Pasquini Neto et al., 2025).

Herd characteristics

Herd characteristics parameters are listed in section 2.1.2 above. Several of those (θ_s , ι_s , ε_s , γ_s) are herd structure averages expressed on an animal unit basis. The liveweight parameter, $LW_{c,s}$, is also an average across different animal cohorts and over time.

To generate parameter values for these, we used a detailed beef cattle herd module in the ClimAg model (Wirsenius, 2024). This herd module includes seven separately modeled animal cohorts, with each cohort being described in terms of liveweight, liveweight gain per day, mortality rates, culling rates, exit ages (e.g., weaning age, slaughter age), and carcass yield. For the cow, additional parameters are calving rate, lactation period and milk production. This description is done separately for the wet and dry seasons. Mathematically, each animal cohort category is modeled as a stock-flow system. This means that the module calculates the number of animals (stock) in each cohort as a function of the entry rates and exit rates (flows) into and out of the cohort. Furthermore, the average

Table 2 Herd and feed characteristics in systems of different productivity in Brazilian beef production. Blank cells mean not applicable. For comments and sources, see table footnotes.

	Ext. 1	Ext. 2	Semi1	Semi2
Herd¹				
Average liveweight of adult animals (incl. calves) (kg)	400	450	450	450
Average liveweight of male growing (ex. feedlot animals) (kg)	340	350	340	270
Average liveweight of female weaned growing (kg)	240	270	270	270
Calving rate (life born calves/cow/year)	0.60	0.80	0.80	0.80
Age at first calving (months)	40	36	36	36
Share adult (incl. calves) cohort of herd, t_s (on AU basis)	47%	50%	54%	56%
Share weaned growing cohort (excl. feedlot animals) of herd, θ_s (on AU basis)	53%	50%	46%	39%
Share males of weaned growing cohort, γ_s (on AU basis)	74%	74%	69%	55%
Share feedlot animals of herd, ε_s (annual avg, on AU basis)				5.5%
Max LW loss adults dry season, $minLWG_{i,dry,adult,s}^{AU}$ (kg/day) ²	0.30	0.15	0.15	0.15
Liveweight gain of feedlot animals (kg/head/day)				1.2
Carcass yield of adult animals (per liveweight)	48.3%	48.3%	48.3%	48.3%
Carcass yield of male growing animals (per liveweight)	50.7%	50.7%	50.7%	50.7%
Carcass yield female growing animals (per liveweight)	53.4%	53.4%	53.4%	53.4%
Pixel-specific modeled feed intake³ (kg DM AU⁻¹ day⁻¹)				
Maximum herbage intake, <i>adults, wet</i> season	8.8 (8.0)	8.6 (8.6)	8.6 (8.6)	8.6 (8.6)
Maximum herbage intake, <i>male growing, wet</i> season	8.6 (7.0)	8.6 (7.1)	8.5 (7.0)	8.5 (5.8)
Maximum herbage intake, <i>female growing, wet</i> season	8.3 (5.2)	8.5 (5.8)	8.5 (5.8)	8.5 (5.8)
Maximum herbage intake, <i>adults, dry</i> season	7.4 (6.8)	7.5 (7.5)	7.5 (7.5)	7.5 (7.5)
Maximum herbage intake, <i>male growing, dry</i> season	7.4 (6.0)	7.4 (6.1)	7.5 (6.1)	7.3 (5.0)
Maximum herbage intake, <i>female growing, dry</i> season	7.3 (4.6)	7.2 (4.9)	7.2 (4.9)	7.2 (4.9)
Pixel-wide predetermined feed intake⁴ (kg DM AU⁻¹ day⁻¹)				
Concentrate supplements, dry season			0.70	0.50
Feedlot period (months)				3
Feedlot feed (per animal units in feedlot)				9.0
Urea	0.010	0.013	0.013	0.017
Mineral salt ⁵	0.060	0.060	0.060	0.060
Feed digestibility (MJ DE (kg DM)⁻¹)				
Herbage, wet season ⁶	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0
Herbage, dry season ⁵	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
Maize silage				12.5
Concentrate supplements			16.5	16.5

AU: animal unit (= liveweight^{0.75}/450^{0.75}), DM: dry matter, DE: digestible energy

¹ See text for sources.

² For Extensive 1, an accumulated weight loss of 10% of liveweight during the dry season was assumed as upper limit. For a dry season of five months, the daily maximum weight loss becomes approx. 0.3 kg. For the systems Ext. 2, Semi 1 and 2, whose calving rates are higher than Ext 1, half of this value was assumed.

³ As described in section 2.1.3, in the stocking rate module, herbage intake is calculated as a fraction of maximum herbage intake, $maxHI_{c,t}^{AU}$. The numbers shown here were based on RUMINANT estimates of *ad lib* intake. Numbers in parentheses refer to feed intake per *actual* heads.

⁴ As described in section 2.1.4, the use of supplementary feed is fixed across pixels, in terms of use per animal unit. All numbers are *averages over entire herd* and year on an animal-unit basis. Concentrates include protein concentrates. Supplements are fed only to growing-finishing bulls at an amount corresponding to 0.7% of liveweight in Semi-intensive 2 in line with Corrêa et al. (2000), and 0.6% of liveweight in Semi-intensive 1.

⁵ For animals not in feedlot. Animals in feedlot received 0.2 kg AU⁻¹ day⁻¹.

⁶ Numbers based on (Euclides, 2001) and RUMINANT model data (Herrero et al., 2013).

liveweight of a cohort is not an exogenous constant but an endogenous parameter calculated using a daily time step.

By assuming a priori values on average liveweight gain rates, we used ClimAg to calculate the average a priori values on liveweights of each cohort (adult+calves, male growing, and female growing) and the herd structures, θ_s , ι_s , ε_s , γ_s , see Table 2. The values of the liveweight gain rates, and those for all other herd parameters, as listed in the previous paragraph, were based on a large body of literature. For the extensive systems, we relied mainly on (Corrêa et al., 2005; Costa et al., 2005, 2008; FNP, 2014a; Pereira et al., 2005; Wirsenius et al., 2025), and for the semi-intensive mainly on (Corrêa et al., 2000; FNP, 2014b). Data for feedlot operations were mainly based on (FNP, 2014c; Ribeiro et al., 2012). For all systems, we also relied on (Cardoso et al., 2016; Pasquini Neto et al., 2025).

Supplementary feed use

As described in section 2.1.4, the use of supplementary feed per animal unit is fixed across pixels. However, the use of supplementary feed per hectare, and hence cost per hectare and per kg of beef output, is pixel-specific since it depends on stocking rate and liveweight gain rates.

We assumed that mineral salt and urea are fed to all animals in all beef systems. For concentrate feed, we assumed use in the semi-intensive systems only. In those systems, concentrates are fed only to growing-finishing bulls during the dry season at an amount corresponding to 0.7% of liveweight in Semi-intensive 2 in line with Corrêa et al. (2000), and 0.6% of liveweight in Semi-intensive 1. The concentrate ration consists of 80% maize grains, 19% soybean meal, and 1% urea (numbers on dry matter basis), with crude protein content of about 20%. The dry season was defined as the period of consecutive months with less than 70 mm of monthly rainfall, based on (Köppen, 1936).

The feedlot ration in Semi-intensive 2 consists of 40% maize silage, 50% maize grains, 7.5% soybean meal, 0.7% urea and 2.0% mineral salt (numbers on a dry matter basis), based on (Corrêa et al., 2000; FNP, 2014c).

Fertilizer and lime application

At pasture renewal, lime and NPK fertilizer are applied. For all systems, we based the rates of application on FNP (FNP, 2014d). In the system Extensive 1, we assumed 1.5 Mg lime per hectare and 250 kg NPK per hectare, and in Extensive 2, Semi-intensive 1 and Semi-intensive 2, 2.0 Mg lime per hectare and 500 kg NPK per hectare (Table 10).

In all systems except Extensive 1, urea fertilizer and lime are applied annually on all pasture areas. As described in section 2.1.4, the rate of these inputs is calculated as a coefficient multiplied by the pixel-specific modeled herbage intake. We estimated the value of these coefficients using the ClimAg model, which, in addition to the herd module mentioned above, also includes a highly detailed representation of nitrogen cycling across animals and land (see Table 9 for numbers).

3.1.3 Herbage growth and intake

Herbage growth and senescence

We estimated rates of herbage growth and senescence (to surface) per ha using the crop systems model DSSAT, which simulates growth and development as a function of soil-plant-atmosphere dynamics (Jones et al., 2003). For estimating herbage productivity, DSSAT was run using the CROPGRO module for *Brachiaria decumbens*. Soil data were taken from the Harmonized World Soil Database (FAO/IIASA/ISRIC/ISSCAS/JRC, 2012). For pixels containing more than one soil type, the dominant soil was used. Climate data were taken from MarkSim. DSSAT was executed in daily time steps, over 20 years of climate data (more specifically, five repetitions of four years of simulated climate data). For these runs, model output on growth and senescence rates in each pixel was aggregated to monthly averages for one year. Additional model output used here was specific leaf area and leaf mass fraction of total plant mass above ground, which are used for calculating herbage intake, see below.

To simulate the two different types of pasture management assumed in the beef systems as described in section 3.1.2, we ran DSSAT for two different treatments: i) Unfertilized pasture, with an input of 5 kg N fertilizer ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ (similar to atmospheric nitrogen deposition), and ii) Fertilized pasture, with an input of 200 kg N fertilizer ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. This rate was assumed to be high enough not to significantly limit DSSAT yield estimates. As described above, the actual N fertilization rate in each pixel was adjusted according to the herbage growth and intake at each pixel. For both nitrogen treatments, DSSAT was run for four years after planting to reach the steady-state condition characteristic of each. The monthly averages for this 4-year period were used as estimates for each treatment.

Grazed herbage intake

As described in section 2.1.3, herbage intake by one individual animal is calculated as a fraction of maximum herbage intake, $maxHI_{c,t}^{AU}$. The numbers on maximum herbage intake were based on the RUMINANT model estimates of *ad lib* intake, see Table 2. The intake fraction of maximum is calculated from the leaf area index, as shown in Eq. 1, which in turn is calculated from the monthly average herbage pool (Eq. 2). This in turn, is calculated from the start and end values of the herbage pool (Eq. 3 and Eq. 4), which depends on the herbage intake by all animals (Eq. 5). Hence, the pixel-specific herbage intake is both an input and an output in the herbage growth modeling. An exact analytical solution of this calculation would require hard-linking DSSAT with the stocking rate script in the BeefSC model; however, this was deemed infeasible. Instead, we made several DSSAT runs with different exogenously defined intake rates per month, and soft-linked its output of growth, senescence, specific leaf area, and leaf fraction to the stocking rate optimization module.

Grazing is not explicitly represented in DSSAT, so we mimicked herbage intake by prescribed cutting and removal of herbage mass at specified intervals. Due to limitations in DSSAT design, this cutting was implemented for leaf mass only. Expressed as a fraction of the standing leaf mass cut and removed by the end of each month, the four cutting rates were 30, 40, 50, and 60 percent, respectively. These cuttings were applied at three different time intervals (spells), 30, 45, and 60 days, meaning that we generated 12 different DSSAT outputs for each pixel and nitrogen fertilizer treatment.

3.1.4 Liveweight gain

We calculated pixel-specific daily liveweight gains by applying Eqs. 1-6 on the herbage pool output from DSSAT (see section 3.1.3). Numerical values of the coefficients in Eq. 6 are given in Table 8.

3.1.5 Stocking rates

We ran the stocking rate optimization script for each of the 12 different DSSAT outputs of growth, senescence, specific leaf area, and leaf mass fraction. The cutting and removal rate in each was used as the proxy for herbage intake in the herbage pool calculations (Eq. 3 and Eq. 4). Thereby, we could calculate the herbage intake per animal unit (Eq. 1) and hence also liveweight gain rate (Eq. 6) for each of these 12 DSSAT outputs. Hence, for each pixel, 12 different estimates of the optima of $SR_{i,s}$ and $\alpha_{i,s}$ were generated (Eq. 7, Eq. 8, and Eq. 9). Among these, the final result was selected that yielded the smallest deviation between calculated herbage intake and the herbage removal prescribed in the cutting regime. More specifically, for each pixel and paddock, the one with the smallest accumulated value of the square number of the monthly discrepancy between herbage intake and herbage removal was selected.

3.1.6 Production costs

Production cost data were originally collated in the year 2014, when this work was initiated (see Acknowledgements). The main data source was *Anuário da Pecuária Brasileira* (ANUALPEC), a comprehensive data collection on Brazilian livestock production produced annually by Informa Economics FNP in São Paulo. Unfortunately, when we resumed this work, this yearbook had been discontinued, and we were unable to obtain more recent data. Therefore, for parameters where we did not find more recent data sources, we estimated current cost levels by adjusting the 2014 cost data in ANUALPEC for inflation in Brazilian currency (R\$) during the period 2014 to 2025.

Operational (variable) costs

We based most of the operational costs on ANUALPEC data, with adjustments for inflation as described above, see Table 9. However, prices on labor, fertilizer, lime and supplementary feed were based on recent data, see Table 3.

Table 3 Prices of labor, beef, fertilizer and purchased feed in Brazilian beef production. Fertilizer, feed and supplement prices refer to those at regional center; farm-gate prices are calculated by adding transportation costs from the nearest regional center to each pixel, see text. For sources, see table footnotes.

Item	Unit	Value
Labor ¹	R\$/ hr	9.9
Beef – cows ²	R\$/Kg	18.4
Beef – steers/bulls ²	R\$/Kg	20.1
Beef – heifers ²	R\$/Kg	10.0
Urea (46% N) ³	R\$/ Mg	1730
Ammonium nitrate (34% N)	R\$/ Mg	1530
NPK fertilizer (10% N)	R\$/ Mg	1580
Lime	R\$/ Mg	140
Maize grains ⁴	R\$/ Mg fresh weight	1510

Item	Unit	Value
Soybean meal ⁵	R\$/ Mg fresh weight	1380
Cottonseed	R\$/ Mg fresh weight	1710
Mineral salt ⁶	R\$/ Mg	1800
Maize silage	R\$/ Mg fresh weight	530

¹ (Carlos et al., 2022).

² (IMEA, 2025)

³ (CONAB, 2025).

⁴ (CONAB, 2022).

⁵ (Agrolink, 2025).

⁶ (Instituto de Economia Agrícola (IEA), 2025).

Fixed costs

We based most of the fixed costs on ANUALPEC data, with adjustments for inflation as described above, see Table 10. Fixed costs are annualized using Eq. 13. For all fixed assets, we assumed a salvage value of zero. For fence cost estimates, we assumed a total farm area of 1000 hectares of pasture.

Transportation costs

We estimated the cost of transporting live cattle to slaughterhouses across Brazil using a raster-based least-cost framework that integrates road infrastructure, freight prices, and slaughterhouse locations. In parallel, we derived a spatially explicit cost surface for transporting inputs to pasturelands by combining travel-time estimates to regional supply centers with national freight cost data.

All monetary values – originally reported in Brazilian reais – were converted to constant 2025 terms using the accumulated Broad National Consumer Price Index (IPCA) from the Central Bank of Brazil.

Transportation costs of live animals to slaughterhouses

As a first step, we obtained vector data on Brazil's road network – including federal, state, and other road sections – from the MapBiomias infrastructure dataset (MapBiomias, 2025), which compiles official cartographic sources produced by the Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (IBGE, 2025). Road segments were classified into two categories – paved and unpaved – and merged into a single national road layer. Because access roads are not comprehensively mapped at the national scale, we assigned access-road transport costs to all pasture pixels – obtained from MapBiomias collection 8 land use and land cover dataset, reclassified from 30 m to 100 m resolution – not intersecting either paved or unpaved road classes. Then, we buffered the vector network by 100 m and rasterized it to a 100-m grid using an Albers Equal Area Conic projection. Locations of slaughterhouses were obtained from the Trase platform (Mempel et al., 2025), which provides georeferenced facility data for Brazil's beef supply chain. These locations were used as destination points for transport cost calculations.

After generating a road layer, we first derived transportation costs for paved roads. We obtained mean freight prices (USD km⁻¹) for different truck categories from Brazil's national road freight price regulation (Agência Nacional de Transportes Terrestres (ANTT), 2025), which establishes reference

freight tariffs by vehicle type. We combined these per-kilometer costs with estimated freight capacity for each truck class based on standard Brazilian livestock transport good-practice guidance (Ministério da Agricultura, Pecuária e Abastecimento. Secretaria de Desenvolvimento Agropecuário e Cooperativismo, 2013). We then expressed freight costs in R\$ kg⁻¹ of liveweight, assuming a representative animal weight of 400 kg (see Table 4). Secondly, to account for higher costs associated with lower-quality infrastructure, we adjusted paved-road transport costs to derive costs for unpaved roads and access roads using relative cost multipliers derived from Englund et al. (2015) (see Table 5).

Table 4 Freight costs for transporting livestock in Brazil. Freight costs are reported for trucks with different numbers of axles, showing the cost per kilometer (2021 USD), the average transport capacity (number of animals, N), and the resulting cost per Mg-kilometer. Cost per Mg-kilometer assumes an average live weight of 400 kg per animal transported to slaughter. Mean values across truck types are shown in the bottom.

Truck type (number of axles)	Cost per km (R\$ km ⁻¹)	Capacity (number of cattle)	Cost per Mg per km (R\$ Mg ⁻¹ km ⁻¹)
2	3.465	16	0.540
3	4.385	25	0.440
5	5.35	32	0.420
6	6.00	36	0.415
Mean all	4.800	27	0.455

Table 5 Transportation costs by road type. Transportation costs for livestock are shown for paved, unpaved, and access roads. Relative cost weights are derived from estimates reported by Englund et al. (2015) and are used to scale the mean transport cost for paved roads to obtain corresponding costs for unpaved and access roads.

Road type	Cost in Englund et al	Weight	Cost per Mg per km (R\$ Mg ⁻¹ km ⁻¹)
Paved	0.080	1	0.455
Unpaved	0.160	2	0.880
Access	0.320	4	1.760

Finally, we calculated cumulative least-cost (cost-distance) surfaces representing the minimum cost of transporting live cattle to the nearest slaughterhouse. This was implemented using the *r.cost* algorithm in GRASS GIS, accessed from R via the *rgrass* package (Bivand and Pawley, 2022). The algorithm computes the accumulated minimum transport cost from each raster cell across the friction surface defined by road-specific transport costs. The resulting raster represents the cumulative cost (R\$ per Mg of liveweight) of transporting cattle from any pasture area in Brazil to the nearest slaughterhouse.

Transportation costs of fertilizer and concentrates from regional centers

We used the global travel-time-to-cities raster developed by (Weiss et al., 2018), which integrates road networks, terrain, land cover, and human mobility constraints to estimate travel time (in minutes) to the nearest urban center at a 1 km spatial resolution. From this dataset, we retained only cities with populations of at least 100,000 inhabitants, which we assumed represent regional centers capable of supplying agricultural inputs at scale. The resulting raster, therefore, represents travel time from each 1-km pixel to the nearest qualifying regional center.

We derived a representative freight cost per kilometer from Brazil's national road freight price regulation (ANTT, 2025) averaging across truck classes with different axle numbers. This yielded a

mean freight cost of R\$ 3.20 km⁻¹. To ensure compatibility with the travel-time raster, we converted this value to a cost per unit time by assuming an average truck speed of 50 km h⁻¹, resulting in a freight cost of R\$ 2.675 min⁻¹.

We multiplied the cost-per-minute estimate by the travel-time raster to obtain a spatially explicit surface of transportation costs from regional centers. Finally, we masked this surface using our pastureland map, retaining values only for pixels currently classified as pasture. The resulting layer represents the estimated minimum transportation cost (R\$ tonne⁻¹) for moving fertilizer and concentrate inputs from regional centers to ranchlands.

Pixel-level cost calculations

For cost items with constant prices across pixels, output from the detailed modeling of operational and fixed costs was aggregated and scaled to three key variables: i) pasture area, ii) stocking rate, and iii) annual herbage intake per hectare of pasture, see Table 6. The cost coefficients in Table 6 were then applied to the pixel-specific estimates of stocking rates ($SR_{i,s}$, Eq. 9) and herbage intakes ($HI_{i,s}^{yr}$, Eq. 10) from the stocking-rate module to produce pixel-specific cost estimates of the on-farm production costs.

For cost items whose prices vary by pixel, primarily fertilizer and feed, pixel-specific quantities were first calculated, and then the pixel-specific prices were applied, see Table 9 for quantity input data and Table 3 at regional centers. The pixel-specific prices were calculated as the sum of the price at the regional center plus the transportation cost per unit, as described in the previous section (Eq. 12).

Table 6 Cost coefficients in Brazilian beef production for cost items with constant prices across pixels. The table shows annual cost coefficients and their scaling unit. Costs for fertilizer, lime, purchased feed, supplements, and labor are calculated using pixel-specific prices (see Eq. 12) applied to pixel-specific quantities (given in Table 9).

Cost coefficient	Unit (all per year)	Ext 1	Ext 2	Semi 1	Semi 2
Operational costs					
Pasture labor and machinery	R\$ per ha pasture	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Pasture fertilizer and lime application	R\$ per Mg herbage intake	1.2	4.6	4.7	5.1
Breeding bulls	R\$ per animal unit (AU)	13.7	13.6	14.2	15.7
Vaccination, vet & medical	R\$ per animal unit (AU)	32	34	40	46
Machinery other than for pasture	R\$ per animal unit (AU)	35	50	50	54
Repairs	R\$ per ha pasture	18	26	27	27
Interest on operating capital	per operational cost excl. interest and taxes	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Property tax (ITR)	R\$ per ha pasture	13.7	13.7	13.7	13.7
Administration, etc.	per operational cost excl. interest and taxes	0.075	0.075	0.075	0.075
Fixed costs					
Pasture establishment ex. fertilizer, lime	R\$ per ha pasture	66	60	60	60
Animals	R\$ per animal unit (AU)	45	54	56	62
Fences	R\$ per ha pasture	19	19	19	19
Waterers	R\$ per ha pasture	6.5	11	12	11
Buildings	R\$ per animal unit (AU)	30	30	30	40
Machinery	R\$ per animal unit (AU)	35	35	35	35

The total pixel-specific annual on-farm costs were divided by the pixel-specific total annual output in the form of live animals, as calculated in the stocking rate optimization, to obtain the farm-gate cost per kg of output. The transportation costs to abattoirs, as described above, were added to this to obtain the cost per kg at market.

3.1.7 Results

Table 7 presents the estimated costs of the four beef systems as median values across all pixels. The cost per hectare is significantly higher in the more intensive systems than in Extensive 1. However, due to higher beef yields, the cost per kg of beef increases less. Importantly, most of the higher costs in the more intensive systems are operational costs, primarily for feed and fertilizer purchases. The increases in investment (fixed) costs are relatively small and are mainly due to a more frequent renewal of pastures (every 15 years instead of 25).

Figure 1 shows the variation in costs per kg of beef across pixels. The spread in costs is larger in extensive systems, particularly in Extensive 1. In extensive systems, fixed costs make up a larger fraction of total costs, since the costs of fences, waters, corrals, and other facilities are the same as in systems with higher productivity, which have higher operational costs because of the use of fertilizers and supplementary feed. This means that, in pixels with low herbage growth per hectare, fixed costs per beef output per hectare become high.

Figure 2 Figure 1 shows estimated optimal stocking rates in the systems. The median stocking rate is almost twice as high in the more intensive systems as in Extensive 1. This is almost entirely due to that pasture areas are fertilized annually in the intensive systems, but not in Extensive 1.

Table 7 Median values of estimated costs and productivity in Brazilian beef systems of different intensity.

Parameter	Unit	Ext 1	Ext 2	Semi 1	Semi 2
Costs					
Total costs per hectare of pasture	R\$/ha	708	1,730	2,290	3,210
Total costs per beef carcass produced	R\$/kg	16.6	19.3	18.8	23.2
% fixed cost	% of total	40%	27%	21%	16%
Pasture excl. annual fertilizer and lime	% of total	17%	12%	9.0%	6.4%
Fertilizer and lime	% of total	4.6%	28%	23%	18%
Supplement feed	% of total	9.6%	6.5%	23%	37%
Facilities, machinery, equipment	% of total	25%	18%	14%	12%
Labor	% of total	16%	11%	8.5%	5.9%
Transportation of inputs and outputs	% of total	3.2%	3.0%	3.1%	2.6%
Other (animals, etc)	% of total	24%	21%	19%	17%
Biophysical productivity					
Stocking rate per ha of pasture – average all animals	AU/ha	1.35	2.25	2.40	2.54
Feed intake per ha – total all animals	Mg DM/ha/year	3.9	6.0	6.5	6.9
Liveweight gain per ha– total all animals	kg/ha/day	80	160	230	260
Liveweight gain per animal– average all animals	kg/AU/day	0.16	0.20	0.26	0.28
Carcass production per ha of pasture – total all animals	kg/ha/year	46	88	120	140

Figure 3 shows liveweight gain per hectare of growing animals. The relative increases in liveweight gain rates in the intensive system vs. Extensive 1 are larger than for the relative increases in stocking rates, which is due to that the liveweight gain per animal is higher in the intensive systems (see Table 7). This is mainly because in the intensive systems, which use fertilizer to obtain higher herbage yields, a smaller fraction of the pasture area is needed to sustain the cows, which means that a larger area can be allocated to the growing animals, leading to higher intake and growth per animal. For Semi-intensive systems 1 and 2, supplementary feeding during the dry season and feedlot finishing add to further increases in liveweight gain at the herd level.

A: Extensive 1

B: Extensive 2

C: Semi-intensive 1

D: Semi-intensive 2

Figure 2 Estimated costs per kg of beef carcass produced in Brazilian beef systems of different intensity.

A: Extensive 1

B: Extensive 2

C: Semi-intensive 1

D: Semi-intensive 2

Figure 3 Optimal stocking rates for Brazilian beef systems of different intensity. Graphs show animals on pasture areas only, excluding those in feedlots (applies to system Semi-intensive 2 only).

A: Extensive 1

B: Extensive 2

C: Semi-intensive 1

D: Semi-intensive 2

Figure 4 Liveweight gain per year of growing animals in Brazilian beef systems of different intensity. Graphs show liveweight gain on pasture areas only, excluding those in feedlots (applies to system Semi-intensive 2 only).

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Appendices

Table 8 Coefficients for estimating liveweight changes from grazed intake in Brazilian beef production. See sections 2.1.5 and 3.1.4 for details.

System and animal cohort	Coefficient ϕ	Coefficient χ	Coefficient ψ	r^2
Extensive 1				
Adult animals, wet season	-0.0413	0.886	-4.15	99.7%
Adult animals, dry season	-0.0604	1.03	-4.08	99.7%
Male growing animals, wet season	-0.0077	0.289	-1.31	99.9%
Male growing animals, dry season	-0.0333	0.581	-2.30	99.9%
Female growing animals, wet season	-0.0048	0.253	-1.25	99.8%
Female growing animals, dry season	-0.101	1.51	-5.47	99.3%
Extensive 2				
Adult animals, wet season	-0.0332	0.766	-3.73	99.7%
Adult animals, dry season	-0.0613	1.03	-4.07	99.8%
Male growing animals, wet season	-0.0098	0.320	-1.42	99.8%
Male growing animals, dry season	-0.0522	0.839	-3.17	98.3%
Female growing animals, wet season	-0.0137	0.381	-1.69	99.3%
Female growing animals, dry season	-0.0597	0.956	-3.65	99.2%
Semi-intensive 1				
Adult animals, wet season	-0.0332	0.766	-3.73	99.7%
Adult animals, dry season	-0.0613	1.03	-4.07	99.8%
Male growing animals, wet season	-0.0051	0.253	-1.18	99.8%
Male growing animals, dry season ²	-0.0139	0.284	-0.555	96.7%
Female growing animals, wet season	-0.0137	0.381	-1.69	99.3%
Female growing animals, dry season	-0.0597	0.956	-3.65	99.2%
Semi-intensive 2				
Adult animals, wet season	-0.0332	0.766	-3.73	99.7%
Adult animals, dry season	-0.0613	1.03	-4.07	99.8%
Male growing animals, wet season	-0.0042	0.242	-1.18	99.9%
Male growing animals, dry season ²	-0.0121	0.265	-0.452	97.1%
Female growing animals, wet season	-0.0137	0.381	-1.69	99.3%
Female growing animals, dry season	-0.0597	0.956	-3.65	99.2%

Table 9 Operational cost input data for Brazilian beef systems Blank cells mean not applicable. For sources, see table footnotes.

Type and category	Item	Unit	Ext 1	Ext 2/ Semi 1/ Semi 2
Items with pixel-specific physical quantities and prices¹				
PASTURE				
	Urea (46% N)	kg/kg DM intake	0	0.043; Semi 2: 0.049
	Lime	kg/kg DM intake	0.060	0.060
LABOR				
	Livestock labor – non-feedlot	hours/AU/year	8.3	Ext 2/Semi 1: 8.3; Semi 2: 7.9
	Livestock labor – feedlot	hours/head/batch	n.a.	Ext 2/Semi 1: n.a.; Semi 2: 0.5
SUPPLEMENTS – all year				
	Urea	kg/AU/day	0.010	Ext 2/Semi 1: 0.013; Semi 2: 0.017
	Mineral salt	kg/AU/day	0.060	0.060
FEED purchased – non feedlot – dry season				
	Maize grains	kg/AU/day	0	Semi 1: 0.7; Semi 2: 0.5
	Soymeal/cottonseed	kg/AU/day	0	Semi: 0.1
FEED purchased – feedlot				
	Maize grains	kg/feedlot-AU/day	0	Semi 2: 5.3
	Soymeal/cottonseed	kg/feedlot-AU/day	0	Semi 2: 0.8
	Maize silage	kg/feedlot-AU/day	0	Semi 2: 11.2
Items with constant prices (not varying by pixel)²				
PASTURE				
	Labor and machinery	R\$/ha/year	5	5
	Fertilizer applic. (fuel, labor, etc.)	R\$/Mg fertilizer	-	80
	Lime application (fuel, labor, etc.)	R\$/Mg lime	20	20
ANIMALS				
	Breeding bulls	R\$/AU/year	13.6	13.6
	Vaccines	R\$/calf born	32	Ext 2: 32; Semi: 42
	Vet & medical	R\$/AU/year	23	Ext 2/Semi 1: 23; Semi 2: 27
FACILITIES, MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT				
	Fuel, labor etc – non-feedlot	R\$/AU/year	35	50
	Fuel, labor etc – feedlot	R\$/head/batch	n.a.	Ext 2/Semi 1: n.a.; Semi 2: 20
	Fence facilities repair	of initial cost	0.03	0.03
	Water facilities repair	of initial cost	0.08	0.08
	Other facilities/machinery repair	of initial cost	0.01	0.01
OTHER				
	Interest on operating capital	of half oper. costs	0.06	0.06
	Other (administration, etc)	of oper. costs excl. taxes and interest	0.075	0.075
	Property tax ITR	R\$/ha/year	13.7	13.7

¹ Urea and fertilizer use based on the ClimAg model, see text. Labor use based on (FNP, 2014e, 2014f). Use of supplements and purchased feed from Table 2.

² Based on (FNP, 2014e, 2014f). Property tax was calculated using the average statutory rate of 0.18% of declared property value, as reported by Appy and Moutinho (2015). Updated spatially explicit property values were taken from d'Albertas et al. (2024) and multiplied by this rate to estimate annual ITR payments per hectare. Tax values were first computed at the pixel level and then averaged across all pixels to obtain the mean national ITR value used in the analysis

Table 10 Fixed cost input data for Brazilian beef systems All assets were assumed to having zero salvage value. Blank cells mean not applicable. For sources, see table footnotes.

Category	Item	Unit	Ext 1	Ext 2/ Semi 1/ Semi 2
GENERAL DATA				
	Interest rate on investment	of average investment cost ¹	6%	6%
	Insurance rate on facilities	of initial cost	0.25%	0.25%
PASTURE ²				
	Lime requirement	Mg/ha	1.5	2.0
	NPK fertilizer requirement	Mg/ha	0.25	0.5
	Seeds requirement	kg/ha	12	6.0
	Machinery cost	R\$/ha	500	500
	Labor requirement	hours/ha	5.0	5.0
	Lifetime	years	25	15
	Amortized cost	R\$/ha/year	150	240
ANIMALS ³				
	Cow cost	R\$/liveweight	8.0	8.0
	Lifetime of cow	years	10	10
	Amortized cost	R\$/AU/year	45	Ext 2: 54; Semi 1: 56; Semi 2: 62
FACILITIES, MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT				
Fences ⁴				
	Perimeter fence requirement	m/ha	36	36
	Permanent internal fence requirement	m/ha	24	24
	Temporary internal fence requirement	m/ha	6.0	6.0
	Perimeter fence cost	R\$/m	9.0	9.0
	Permanent internal fence cost	R\$/m	9.0	9.0
	Temporary internal fence cost	R\$/m	3.5	3.5
	Perimeter fence lifetime	years	25	25
	Permanent internal fence lifetime	years	25	25
	Temporary internal fence lifetime	years	9.0	9.0
	Amortized cost all fences	R\$/ha/year	19	19
Watering facilities ⁵				
	Waterers requirement	liter capacity/AU	50	50
	Waterers cost (including piping etc)	R\$/liter capacity	1.0	1.0
	Amortized cost	R\$/ha/year	6.5	11
Buildings ⁶				
	Corral & chute	R\$/AU	200	200
	Feed bunks mineral salt	R\$/AU	20	20
	Feed bunks etc suppl. feed - unroofed	R\$/AU grazing stock	40	40
	Machinery depot	R\$/AU	50	50
	Open drylot - earthen pen	R\$/AU feedlot batch	n.a.	Ext 2/Semi 1: n.a.; Semi 2: 80
	Feed storage & processing depot	R\$/AU	n.a.	Ext 2/Semi 1: n.a.; Semi 2: 50
	Corral & chute lifetime	years	20	20
	Feed bunks mineral salt lifetime	years	5	5
	Feed bunks etc suppl. feed lifetime	years	10	10
	Machinery depot lifetime	years	30	30
	Open drylot lifetime	years	n.a.	Ext 2/Semi 1: n.a.; Semi 2: 20
	Feed storage & processing depot lifetime	years	n.a.	Ext 2/Semi 1: n.a.; Semi 2: 30
	Amortized cost all buildings	R\$/AU/year	30	Ext 2/Semi 1: 30; Semi 2: 40
Machinery ⁷				

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Category	Item	Unit	Ext 1	Ext 2/ Semi 1/ Semi 2
	Feeding, livest mgmt, etc	R\$/AU total stock	350	350
	Lifetime	years	15	15
	Amortized cost	R\$/AU/year	35	35

¹ Interest cost is the interest rate multiplied by average investment cost, which is calculated as initial cost minus salvage value divided by two.

² Based on (FNP, 2014d).

³ Purchasing price based on price data in Table 3.

⁴ Based on (FNP, 2014g, 2014h). We assumed a total grazing area of 1000 hectare and a perimeter fence requirement equaling the square root of the area multiplied by five.

⁵ Based on (Barreto and Silva da Silva, 2013).

⁶ Based on Embrapa data, (FNP, 2014i).

⁷ Based on Embrapa data.